

IMPACT OF ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE, TRAINING & LEADERSHIP ON EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE IN SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES (SMEs) OF KARACHI

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ABSTRACT

Examining how organizational culture, leadership, and training impact employee performance is the goal of this study. This research is a quantitative research with a case study at the SME's Company in Karachi by distributing questionnaires to 150 employees. SPSS was used to process the data. The findings revealed that the respondents did, in fact, believe that organizational culture and Training had direct significant effect on employee performance, and Leadership could not rely on employee performance. Organizational culture has a significant direct effect on employee performance and training has a significant direct effect on employee. Where all relationships lead in a positive direction except leadership. There hasn't been any study that looks at the relationship model of those four factors in order to ascertain their wider relationships and This study gives a broad overview of employee behaviors in SME's and is helpful as a starting point for developing strategies, particularly for businesses looking to boost performance.

KEYWORDS: *Organizational Culture, Training & Leadership, Employee Performance*

INTRODUCTION

This study aim at examining the effects of organizational culture, leadership, and training on employees' performance. There are three main things which are very important for employee performance, the primary factor is company culture, which has an impact on all facets of your organization, including tone of voice and timeliness as well as contract conditions and employee benefits. Organizational culture has been identified as a significant valuable resource and a barrier to imitation, as well as a variable that profoundly affects productivity (Joseph & Kibera, 2019). Your employees are inclined to feel comfortable when the workplace culture matches their preferences. A positive work culture promotes productivity, engagement, and improves employee's experiences. Every employee possesses the capacity depending on his or her knowledge, abilities, and competences that are suited to the position, as well as on their , job satisfaction, leadership style, corporate culture, and personalities, attitudes, and behaviors (Mubarak ,2019).With a good organization culture, you also need to offer training and development. Training is important for improving employee performance since every business needs skilled and experienced workers to carry out their tasks. Performance is the result of someone working hard to do something tasks entrusted to him relying on his abilities, experience, sincerity, and timing (Sabban, 2020). Training also shapes workers' knowledge, skills, behavior, and attitudes toward the demands of their jobs. One of the main operational tasks in human resource management is training. According to a study by (Haryono et al., 2020).Companies with excellent staff training initiatives can boost workers' work performance. All firms that want to boost worker performance must put a strong emphasis on staff training. The third factor is a competent leader who can effectively communicate, manage and allocate tasks, pay attention to criticism, and address problems in a constantly changing workplace. Therefore, having the correct kind of leaders is strongly recommended for the organization in order to increase production and efficiency (Agarwal, 2020).

In a broader sense, culture means the complex whole people learn from socialization and implicit cultural transmission that consists of knowledge, ideas, art, ethical practices, and customs.

Schooling within a given society (Joseph & Kibera, 2019). Although many definitions of organizational culture have been put out by scholars (Joseph & Kibera, 2019), the base of culture is comprised of the fundamental underlying assumptions that the majority of organizational members. It's important to be able to adjust your methods to fit the local culture. This does not imply, however, that one has to permanently adopt a new mindset in place of the previous one (Mubarok, 2019). Leaders in care of people management training generate various exercise programs to put personnel in a position where they can fulfil their duties and acquire the needed skills, knowledge, and capabilities (Halawi et al., 2018). The importance of leadership in an organization can be seen in how it contributes to the formulation of the firm vision, mission, and goals as well as the design of its strategies and policies for achieving those goals in an efficient and effective way (Agarwal, 2020). Holding training package where One method to raise employee performance in the company is to execute a program that was established with the requirements of the company in mind. (Niati et al., 2021). Training serves as one of among the most important aspects of a worker's career growth. The outcomes of previous study by (Niati et al., 2021a) who revealed that training takes such an affect that is straight related to career progression, provide evidence for this. Performance results show how well major stakeholders, including customers, staff, and shareholders, were able to balance their competing interests (Joseph & Kibera, 2019). The current study will help determine whether adopting collaborative as well as transformational leadership styles has any effect on employees' performance; if so, whether that impact is significant or otherwise; and, in addition time, it will assess the degree to which performance varies as a result of endorsed leadership styles (Agarwal, 2020).

INDUSTRY BRIEF

Small and medium-sized businesses, also known as SMEs, are self-regulatory businesses that typically employ fewer people than a predetermined threshold. Small industries are typically ones with fewer than 50 employees. We are focusing on SMEs (small to medium-sized firms) in this research because they are an important part of the economy of a nation.

RESEARCH PROBLEM

Organization culture, Training, Leadership has a key influence on employee performance. The research is on the SME's of Karachi, Sindh Pakistan. Some research hypothesis proved that these variables have significant but these researches on specific industries (Shahzad, 2014). Our research include all the SME's of Karachi.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

To check the impact of organization culture on employee performance.

To check the impact of leadership on employee performance.

To check the impact of training on employee performance.

JUSTIFICATION

This research is being conducted for the peoples who are facing various problem in the enterprises either small or medium and for those who are going to start their business now, so the reason of this research is to aware them that what is the importance of training, leaders, and a good culture in any organization for achieving their target and for employees sustainability.

LIMITATION

We have selected only SMEs (small medium enterprises) of Karachi so this research is limited to the SMEs of Karachi only

SCOPE

As we can see, many people started small enterprises just after COVID cycle as a result of losing their jobs. Small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs) are essential to the world economy and perform a crucial role in economic growth by supplying goods and services, promoting industrialization, establishing managerial skills to boost national wealth, and, most importantly, by employing residents of the nation. There are always certain challenges like culture, how to teach someone to be a wonderful employee, and how to manage them to produce flawless results whenever we launch any firm. We must all learn how to deal with these issues in the modern period if we want to preserve our businesses in the marketplace. His goal as a pioneer is to increase employee engagement, make a business better at filling talent pipeline shortages, and cut down on the difficulties and costs associated with turnover. Kinds of leaders attract, hire, and motivate excellent people. Management of training, or the activities that focus on strengthening a person's skills in management and leadership is also very important. Soft skills like empathy and communications may be given more weight because they foster better teamwork and deeper relationships with the individuals they manage.

ASSUMPTIONS

People might make the assumption that there is no need for proper training for a small business.

Some people make assumptions that we don't need a maintained culture for organization.

People might make assumptions that everyone can do their task without any leader or a focus person in the organization.

LITERATURE REVIEW

An organization must pay close attention to performance. The institute will be capable to participate successfully with excellent employee performance. Performance is a learning outcome that an individual or a group of persons within a business can attain, in according with their specific powers and objectives, in an endeavor to uphold morality and ethics while remaining within the bounds of the law and in conformity with the objectives of the relevant organization (Wahjoedi, 2021). Many variables that affect each person's performance can be divided into three categories, specially the person's own competence of help from the general people, the company, and management (Wahjoedi, 2021). Several factors motivates organizational culture, training, leadership and employee performance.

ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE

Organizational culture serves businesses as (Mubarak, 2019) 1) to provide employees a sense of organizational identity; 2) to demonstrate a group commitment; 3) to encourage the stability of the social structure; and 4) to create behaviors by assisting managers in being aware of them. According to(Mubarak, 2019) , how an organization's culture work 1) the responsibility for carrying out duties in the human resources sector; 2) an approach for creating the businesses' plans. According to (Meng & Berger, 2019). The organizational atmosphere of a company is its shared beliefs, values, and presumptions. Such core interests have an impact on organizational members' behaviors because they rely only on norms to inform their choices and behaviors, which additional has an effect on the performance of a firm (Meng & Berger, 2019). Organizational associates build a combination of mutually agreed ideas and beliefs around by considering organizations as socio-political, sensible, and logical systems, one can determine what is true, what matters, and how to behave. (Meng & Berger, 2019). According to (Joseph & Kibera, 2019), behavior and culture both impact one another and promote learning among organization members as well as the creation of novel solutions to the company's performance-oriented problems. The primary benchmark for the actions and results of the business is the sum of the efforts of each individual member of the organization. Performance evaluation is the top management's role, according to (Joseph & Kibera, 2019). As a outcome, managers deliberately work to produce an organizational values that morals performance. (Joseph & Kibera, 2019) highlight the importance of corporate culture by asserting that for an organization to prosper, its strategy, its structure, and its culture must be successfully linked. Additional support for the hypothesis that organizational culture influences performance through stabilizing individual behavior is provided by (Joseph & Kibera, 2019). Additionally, (Joseph & Kibera, 2019) emphasize organizational culture as a guiding principle that directs organizational behavior in the management's desired direction. The body of extant research indicates a positive relationship between corporate culture and effectiveness. The four organizational culture facets that Denison (Meng & Berger, 2019) identified and validated as having a positive effect on organizational effectiveness are flexibility, consistency, engagement, and mission.

According to (Meng & Berger, 2019), establishing a culture of sharing and working across organizational borders requires a flexible culture in the organization. Additionally, businesses from (Virgiawan et al., 2021). Correspondingly risk-averse organizations will choose to treat it less seriously and build stronger organization structure. Likewise, businesses with a higher tolerance for risk will decide to take additional of them and adopt a softer managerial style.(Virgiawan et al., 2021). The company culture that CEOs create will affect employee performance and strategy, according to numerous studies (Virgiawan et al., 2021). It's important to give employees a voice in the organization. If employees participate in organisational activities, they will feel like a part of the company.

LEADERSHIP

When management is a collaborative effort by a collection of people towards a common goal, teamwork is possible. (Virgiawan et al., 2021). In the field of organizational behavior, "the ability to inspire a group towards accomplishing goals" is referred to as leadership. This leadership style has been extensively researched, makes use of traditional work environments, and is scattered in thoughts (Virgiawan et al., 2021). Another crucial organizational characteristic is leadership, as it greatly influences the direction and ruling mechanisms within businesses (Meng & Berger, 2019). The deployment of a leadership style in an organization is determined by a variety of elements because not all styles are appropriate in all circumstances (Agarwal, 2020). Employee performance is significantly impacted by the actions of leader (Zoechriba et al., 2020). The characteristics of a leader's followers and the importance of communication that takes place between the follower and the leader both have an impact on that leader's performance (Zoechriba et al., 2020). Leadership styles need to be refined and developed through time, even if they draw attention. According to study, competences change according to the circumstances and develop, mature, and emerge throughout time (Virgiawan et al., 2021). In a broad sense, leadership entails the process of setting organizational goals, a worker's conduct inspiring them to attain goals, influencing workers to better the group, as well as the culture (Zoechriba et al., 2020). To better understand how outstanding leadership in public affairs can manage developing difficulties and how

the field may better educate communication professionals for a changing and uncertain future, leadership research has been broadened into a worldwide context (Meng & Berger, 2019). Although the leader occupies the center role, selection is given to the staff in order to increase the employees' involvement and loyalty to the company (Agarwal, 2020).

A transformational leadership style is one that relies on initiative and is used by leaders and for benefit of the group, company, and employees that work for, beside, and under each other. Transformational leaders' primary goal is to enable their team members (Agarwal, 2020). The available research discusses the fact that various types of organizations have six fundamental components, including top management, which is located at the level of the hierarchy, middle management that also operates at the intermediate level of the organization and specialized core, which handles all of the institution's essential and vital tasks (Agarwal, 2020). Another one is the administrative support team, which performs numerous tasks for the organization, such as mailing, upkeep, and clerical work. The ideology, which is located in the organization's core and defines its values, cultures, and beliefs, is what distinguishes it from other organizations (Agarwal, 2020). Excellent influence, inspiring motivation, idealized influence, and situational variables are all components of transformational leadership (Agarwal, 2020). Given the importance placed on the objectives and organizational achievements, this leadership may be essential in nonprofit and public institutions. These company have a high propensity and community-focused goal (Bich & Thai, 2019). A range of tactics, both explicit (like transformative leadership) and implicit (like emotional contagion), can have a positive impact on team dynamics and output.2020 (Zoechriba et al.) .

TRAINING

By expanding their abilities, talents, knowledge, and behavior, training is a technique utilized to mould and equip staff employees so that changes are occurring more smoothly, effectively, and rationally (Niati et al., 2021b). Employees will be able to learn particular information and practice skills that they can use at work in the future with the help of training, in a limited sense (Niati et al., 2021b). According to Halawi et al. (2018) Training is a planned, organized activity that increases the degree of abilities and knowledge required to complete tasks successfully. A person with a leadership style who seems to have managerial power and the ability to persuade others. Leadership, on the other hand, is just what leaders perform; it is the process of taking charge of a team and motivating them to reach a common objective (Sabban, 2020). The trainers, students, resources, and training objectives are all covered by the training indicators.(Niati et al., 2021b) claim that training is a process that entails instructing staff members in things like abilities, behaviors, self-control, and offering skills related to the kind of work they will be doing. According to (Halawi et al., 2018), firms who offer high quality training have been able to increase their revenues three times more than rivals. However, it takes a combination of coordination and strategy to have such higher intensity programs and personnel; it's not a simple task. With this strategy, training that emphasizes employee motivation, skill mastery, and the development of critical thinking abilities can be effectively provided. Last but not least, training must be based on real-world experience as well as classroom instruction to develop abilities that will last in the industry (Halawi et al., 2018).

EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE

Employee productivity is frequently correlated with the company's efforts to innovate new products, as well as with profits, revenue growth, and market share gains (Virgiawan et al., 2021). All facets of modern day life include productivity and significant value. Performance affects every part of business management in the workplace, thus all managerial actions will boost it (Mubarok, 2019). Performance is the amount and level of effort completed by an employee while performing a task allotted to him after fulfilling his duties (Zoechriba et al., 2020). To find success as outlined in the statement of vision, performance is a crucial factor in deciding the organization's orientation. Employee advancement will enable the organization to thrive in a competitive market climate that is unstable (Zoechriba et al., 2020). Employee performance refers to the technical expertise, conceptual knowledge, and personal interaction skills that employees must have in order to accomplish their job duties. (Sabban, 2020) cites productivity, quality of service, supportiveness, ownership, and accountable as measures of employee performance. Work directly tied to organizational and customer goals that also supports the economy produces performance (Mubarok, 2019). Higher aspirations of incentives for high efficiency, a higher affecting commitment towards the organization, highly top achievers additionally showed a larger responsibility to aid the organization in reaching its goals. Every single one of these discoveries was again linked to increased effectiveness in new responsibilities (Virgiawan et al., 2021). Employee morale is improved through performance evaluation, and this encourages employees to take part in innovative projects and makes it simpler to achieve desired results (Virgiawan et al., 2021). There are three specific ways to evaluate an employee's performance, depending on the quantity, value, and punctuality of their output (Zoechriba et al., 2020). The benefit of supervisors who can spot openings and be close to a talent is recognized by businesses with high-performance attainment initiatives. Companies have increasingly focused on implementing a

variety of high-performance HR practices and campaigns, such as instruction, performance appraisal, pay, professional advancement, teamwork, and many more, in order to increase employee performance. (Virgiawan and others, 2021). Mubarok et al, 2019 lists the following guidelines for creating a successful performance management program : (1) business strategy; (2) assessment evaluation ; (3) frequent quality enhancement; (4) growth; (5) establishment of a positive work environment; and (6) agreement, collaboration, and two-way interaction.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Figure 1

HYPOTHESIS

H: Organizational culture significantly effects on employee performance in the SME’s of Karachi.

H1: Training significantly effects on employee performance in the SME’s of Karachi.

H2: Leadership significantly effects on employee performance in the SME’s of Karachi.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

RESEARCH DESIGN

This research uses different independent variables, mediating and a dependent variable. Independent variables are, organizational culture, training and leadership and the dependent variables is employee performance. The simple random sampling method was used by collecting data from the different SMEs of Karachi. This study was conducted to see the impact of organizational culture, training and leadership on the employee performance. This study is a quantitative research, in order to analyze a particular population or sample, quantitative research is performed, the goal of sampling procedures is to test established hypotheses, and they are typically applied randomly while using research tools for data collecting and quantitative/statistical analysis (wahjoedi, 2021). Questionnaires were used as a medium to collect data from the respondents. Questionnaires are helpful in gathering a large number of data and where standardization brings about uniformity in questions ensuring consistency and accuracy.

PROCEDURE

The information gathered for the present research is quantitative and first-hand. Edited, coded, analyzed, and interpreted the field data that had been gathered. After the questionnaire was revised and validated, the analysis was carried out using the SPSS 16.0 Program. To obtain precise figures and per cent of responses to the questions, a manual methodology was also used. Because a Likert Scale were used to elicit the responses, the data was displayed as percent on bar charts, making it possible to undertake statistical examination on the answers that will be obtained (Malhotra 2004).

PARTICIPANTS

For the collection of the data around 15 SMEs of Karachi were targeted and 150 employees’ data was collected through questionnaires.

DATA COLLECTION

The data was collected through questionnaire, 150 employees of the SMEs of Karachi gave their responses. The questionnaire was distributed in both soft and hard copies, the soft copy. The comprises on eighteen statements, each related to the different variable of the study.

POPULATION

In the research, population is the set of individuals from which a researcher collects information in order to conduct research and draw conclusions. The population of this study is made up of fifteen distinct SME's in Karachi, where hard copies and links to questionnaires were both used to distribute.

SAMPLE AND SAMPLING METHOD

This study survey was conducted from 15 different SME's of Karachi, with the sample size of 150 employees. A simple random sampling method was used. The majority of the respondents were male (67.5%) however, the females were in minority (32.5%).

INSTRUMENT SELECTION

The instrument used in this investigation was a questionnaire. This has been selected on the grounds that they are convenient and cost effective. Questionnaires were administered to each given to the Human Resource Officer in charge of training who distributed the questionnaire to staff and was retrieved from staff in distinct span of time, and where the researchers were unable to reach the link of to the questionnaire was sent via email and WhatsApp contacts. The main data gathering instrument used in this research was the questionnaire and this was then supported by field observation to cross-check and confirms the data gathered. The data was edit to check for omissions and consistency of responses in order to ensure the integrity of the data and wholesomeness of the questionnaire.

VARIABLES

In this study, 5 variables were utilized to examine the relationships between them and to determine the role of the mediator and the effects of the independent variables on the dependent variables. Where organizational culture, training and leadership are the independent variables and employee performance is the dependent variable.

LIMITATION AND RESTRICTIONS

This survey was done only in SMEs of Karachi city. For collecting the data, we were unable to reach to some SMEs so we sent the link to the questionnaire.

ANALYSIS PLAN

Regression analysis will be used to get the investigation's findings. The gathered data will be examined using SPSS software for data analysis. Data analysis techniques include reliability testing, correlation analysis, demographic tables, and R.

DEMOGRAPHICS

The data of the respondents are described below by their age, gender and education.

REGRESSION ANALYSIS

The hypothesis will be measured using t statistics, and regression will be exploited to explore the relationship and influence of Independent and Dependent Variables. To assess the predictability and fitness of the model, the ANOVA results will be employed.

DATA ANALYSIS**Model Summary**

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.716 ^a	.513	.503	.49556

R square shows the total variation of the dependent variable that could be enlightened by independent variables. With a value greater than 0.5 R Square demonstrates that the model is effective enough to determine the relation between the dependent and independent variables. And according to the table above the value of R Square is 0.513, and based on our three independent variables TG, LD and OC, it indicates that the model is significant and capable enough to predict the variations in employee performance.

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	37.726	3	12.575	51.207	.000 ^b
	Residual	35.854	146	.246		
	Total	73.580	149			

F statistics is a model fit test that evaluate the association between specified independent variables and the dependent variables. In the above mentioned table the value of F statistics is 51.207 which is greater than 3.14 and this shows that the model is fit, and F significance is 0.00 which is less than 0.05.

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Coefficients Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.076	.254		4.236	.000
	OC	.203	.067	.233	3.051	.003
	LD	.091	.072	.094	1.257	.211
	TG	.468	.080	.480	5.836	.000

Results of the regression model shows that the t statistics value of the organizational culture is 3.052 which is more than 2, and sig<0.05. The value of leadership came out to be 1.257 which is less than 2 and sig>0.05. The value of training is 5.836 and it's more than 2 and sig<0.05.

This clarifies that organizational culture and training, these two independent variables are significant forecasters and leadership is insignificant.

RELIABILITY

Scale: ALL VARIABLES

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.850	4

The reliability test is performed to assess the stability of the responses over the scale. The overall reliability of all the items is about 0.85 that shows 85% consistency of responses over the scale.

FREQUENCIES

		Gender	Age	Education
N	Valid	150	150	150
	Missing	0	0	0
Mean		1.29	1.78	2.27
Median		1.00	2.00	2.00
Mode		1	1	2
Minimum		1	1	2
Maximum		2	4	3

The table above shows that we have composed the data from about 150 employees of SMEs in Karachi and they were of different age groups, gender and had distinct level of education.

FREQUENCY TABLE

Gender		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	106	70.7	70.7	70.7
	Female	44	29.3	29.3	100.0
	Total	150	100.0	100.0	

The 150 respondent employees were of both genders 106 (70.7%) of them were males and the remaining 44 (29.3) were females. This also shows that the ratio of female employees working in SMEs of Karachi is lower than the male employees.

Age		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	18-24	67	44.7	44.7	44.7
	25-34	57	38.0	38.0	82.7
	35-44	18	12.0	12.0	94.7
	Above 45	8	5.3	5.3	100.0
	Total	150	100.0	100.0	

The above table shows that 67 of our respondents ages were in between 18 to 24, 57 of them were about 25 to 34, 18 respondents were in the age group of 35 to 44 and about 8 respondent's age was above 40

EDUCATION		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Graduate	110	73.3	73.3	73.3
	Master	40	26.7	26.7	100.0
	Total	150	100.0	100.0	

The above stated table showcases the qualifications of the employees. The two levels of education we used as options in our questionnaire were Graduate and Master. In total 150 employees 110 were graduates and remaining 40 were masters. It also shows that the share of graduated employees in SMEs are more than masters.

HYPOTHESIS SUMMARY

Hypothesis	T statistics	Significance level	
H: Organizational culture significantly effects employee performance in the SME’s of Karachi.	3.051	0.003	Accepted
H1: Training significantly effects on employee performance in the SME’s of Karachi.	5.836	0.000	Accepted
H2: Leadership has no significant effects on employee performance in the SME’s of Karachi.	1.257	0.211	Rejected

Leadership does not have a direct significant effect on employee performance.(Achmad & Sunaryo, 2020)

CONCLUSION

The research was conducted on employee performance we have chosen above factors to evaluate the performance of employees of SME’s of Karachi. This research was conducted based on three independent variables and one dependent variable and this research are based on Small medium enterprises of Karachi.

The data has been collected from SME’s in Karachi. The data was collected from 15 different companies of Karachi. We have received 150 respondents from employees of reputed organization. By Using the internal reliability test as a basis, the acquired data was evaluated the values of Cronbach’s Alpha shows the 85% consistency of response overall item and based on constructs the reliability is also greater than 85%. The T-Statics of OC is 3.051, LD is 1.257 and TG is 5.836 where OC and TG has positive impact on EP and LD shows negative effect on EP. All constructs show significant reliability and only the LD shows that the consistency of the response on the scale is insignificant. Correlation analysis and regression were applied to analyses the relationships and influences of variables to test hypotheses and Employees performance.

The results of correlation analysis were tested based on a 95% confidence interval and 5% Margin of Error, the results of four variables Organization Culture , Training value shows significant and Leadership shows insignificant value all three factors are determinants of Employees Performance..

LIMITATION AND RECOMMENDATION

The focus of this study approach has been on correct data even if it is founded on acceptable hypotheses that have been evaluated using a normal questionnaire survey. There are some obstacles and restrictions, though that must be addressed the model has undergo testing to determine its stability via cross-sectional data. It is required that it be retested by both cross-sectional and pool data. Second, while this study focuses on how SMEs perceive OC, and LD and TG on EP objective assessments are necessary for determining its true impact. Third, despite the fact that this research was limited to manufacturing, expanding this model to other industries will give further insight into the OC, LD, TG and EP relationship. Fourth, there are further SME’s factors that impact business tactics, including such as judgment making and long-term feasibility, that are not discovered in this study and more aspects, which contain industry position Future studies may find it useful to investigate SME status, partnership conditions, and degree of innovation, revenue, and share of the market. Furthermore, more investigation into the circumstances causing the lowering of different study model elements is strongly advised. The scope of our report's findings may be constrained by the demographics of our research sample, at the very least. The results of the research should be used with caution in different circumstances. We are aware that any study that uses a survey-based methodology typically runs into generalizability issues. It might be challenging to gather a sample that is representative of the full population. Future research, however, needs to be conducted over a greater period of time with data from a larger range of companies, countries, and individuals with a wide variety of experiences.

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